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The Role Of Moral Education In Forming Patriotism And Social Activism In The Minds Of Young People

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Abstract: This article comprehensively discusses the role of moral education in the formation of patriotism and social activism in the minds of the younger generation. In today's era of globalization and increased information pressure, strengthening the spiritual and moral immunity of young people, educating them in the spirit of high moral qualities such as loyalty to the Motherland, social responsibility, humanity, honesty is considered an important issue. The article analyzes the theoretical foundations of moral education, methods and tools in the pedagogical process, as well as ways to form social activism and patriotic feelings in the minds of young people based on moral values in educational institutions and in the family. Also, proposals and recommendations are put forward to increase the effectiveness of moral education.

Keywords: Moral education, patriotism, youth, spiritual values, educational system, social responsibility, pedagogical influence, personal development.

Introduction.

The development, future and solid foundation of each nation are determined by its youth. The worldview, attitude to life, civic position and social activity of the younger generation, in turn, are formed on the basis of the upbringing they receive. Today, in the conditions of globalization processes, information flow and various social threats, raising young people as healthy, conscious and loyal individuals to the Motherland is becoming an urgent task. In particular, moral education plays a decisive role in this process. Because moral education not only determines the behavior of a person, but also forms such high qualities as patriotism, social responsibility, humanity, and hard work in him. The instillation of the national idea, national values and historical memory into the minds of the younger generation is the basis of moral education. This, in turn, ensures the active participation of young people in the life of society and serves to bring them up as initiative and selfless individuals who are not indifferent to social processes. From this point of view, moral education is not only a necessary tool in forming social activity in the minds of young people, but also a factor of strategic importance. This article deeply analyzes the content, forms and methods of this process.

Materials and methods:

A systematic approach is of great importance in studying the issue of forming patriotism and social activity in the minds of young people from a scientific and pedagogical point of view. In this article, we relied on the concept of person-oriented education, the theory of national education and the criteria of the socio-pedagogical

approach as a methodological basis. During the study, the content, means and forms of moral education, the psychological characteristics of young people and the factors determining their active position in society were studied.

The experience of educational work in general schools, academic lyceums and higher educational institutions, state programs, educational concepts, as well as decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on youth policy were analyzed as materials. Also, scientific sources written in the field of modern pedagogy, psychology, sociology, foreign experiences, methodological manuals on the experience of Uzbekistan, and articles in periodicals served as the main sources of information.

The research used observation, questionnaire, interview and content analysis methods. In particular, through questionnaires conducted among young people, their attitude to patriotism, views on moral values and the level of social activity were analyzed. Through these, an attempt was made to determine what methodological approaches are effective in educating young people. On this basis, the ideas put forward in the article were presented based on experimental and theoretical sources.

Analytical discussion:

The formation of patriotism and social activity in the minds of young people is not only an educational process, but also an important social mechanism that ensures the spiritual stability of society. Moral education is at the heart of this process, because moral values form the main criteria for the worldview of the younger generation. The analysis shows that through moral education, young people learn to take life seriously, understand their responsibility to society, and sincerely feel love for their homeland.

Practical observations and surveys show that young people who grow up in an environment where moral education is highly developed are usually more inclined to participate in socially active activities in society, take the initiative and have a deep understanding of their civic duty. On the contrary, in an environment where moral education is neglected, indifference, individualism, social irresponsibility and even aggressive moods are more often observed. This proves that moral education is a factor of national importance, not only for personal development. The results of the analysis also show that the strengthening of the sense of patriotism largely depends on the implementation of moral education in meaningful, modern and psychologically appropriate forms of youth. Specific approaches - theatrical performances, poems about historical figures, participation in social projects, analysis of films about the homeland - awaken in the hearts of young people a sense of pride, responsibility and involvement. Moral education enhances social activity, because it forms a young person as a responsible person not only for his own life, but also for those around him and society as a whole. Therefore, the improvement of the system of moral education is a direct guarantee of social stability and development. In this process, it is becoming

an urgent necessity for the family, educational institutions, the media, religious and cultural organizations to work together.

Conclusion.

The upbringing of the minds of young people in the spirit of high patriotism, social activity and responsibility is the foundation of the development of any society. And the path to this high goal is closely related, first of all, to moral education. Moral education is not just teaching the rules of etiquette, but also the process of forming the ideas of goodness, truthfulness, patriotism, justice and humanity in the human soul. Today, this education should provide young people not only with theoretical knowledge, but also with the ability to prepare for practical life, form civic consciousness and actively participate in the life of society. The results of the study show that young people who grow up in an environment where the moral education system is perfectly established have a conscious approach to life, love their homeland, and are able to correctly assess their role in society. They are proactive, socially responsible, hardworking, and honest. These qualities shape them as true citizens. On the contrary, in an environment where moral education is neglected, indifference, apathy, individualism, and alienation from society increase. Therefore, moral education is a means of uniting society and strengthening it spiritually.

In conclusion, the role of moral education in the formation of patriotism and social activity in the minds of young people is incomparable. In order to successfully implement this process, family education, the school and higher education system, the media and the general public must work together towards a single goal - to raise young people as well-rounded, patriotic and socially responsible individuals. Only then can we raise a generation that will confidently take over the future of the nation.

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